

CYTOGENETIC FEATURES OF CARCINOGENESIS

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Relevance: *at present, the primary multiplicity of tumors is understood as the presence in one person of several independent malignant or benign neoplasms that have arisen synchronously or metachronously. Primary multiple malignant neoplasms (PMN) can develop in one organ, in paired organs or organs of the same system, as well as in organs and systems that are not related to each other by functional dependence.*

The purpose of this study: was to study the cytogenetic features of carcinogenesis in primary multiple malignant neoplasms.

Material and research methods: the study involved patients who were treated at RSNPMTSOiR in 2012-2014. According to generally accepted principles, for the comparative characterization of the cytogenetic features of patients with PMN and with metastatic tumors, the characteristics of karyotypic changes in vitro were studied.

Results of the study and their discussion: it is known that chromosomal instability can cause the movement of DNA outside the nuclei of tumor cells. And this, in turn, can lead to the development of a chronic intracellular inflammatory response and, thus, allows expanding the area of tumor growth. Cytogenetic studies conducted in patients with PMN did not reveal specific chromosome disorders, but chromosomal instability was found in the form of chromosome fragmentation and the presence of gaps. In patients with metastatic tumors, specific chromosome disorders were also not detected, and chromosomal instability was in the form of small fragments and micronuclei. When studying kinetic changes in tumor cells of patients with PMN, a high expression of the proliferation marker Ki-67 was observed. In the cells of the human body, in the process of evolution, a molecular defense mechanism was developed to fight this type of viral damage, activating the cGAS-STING system, a chain of anti-inflammatory antiviral programs. In cells characterized by chromosomal instability, an increased content of cytosolic DNA is observed along with signs of chronic activation of antiviral cGAS-STING proteins. The observed phenomena make it possible to compare the principle of action of tumor cells with

the response of certain types of immune cells, which, as a rule, are activated by infectious agents. At the same time, the functioning of tumor cells is characterized by a rapid transition to an infectious response program or a scenario of pathophysiological reactions under conditions of traumatic injuries in the body.

Conclusion: Our research allows us to conclude that chromosomal instability leads to metastasis. maintaining the autonomic response of the tumor cell to cytosolic DNA. Also, chromosomal instability can cause DNA to move outside the nuclei of tumor cells. And this, in turn, can lead to the development of a chronic intracellular inflammatory response and, thus, allows expanding the area of tumor growth.

Our results are of great interest, as PMNs are an excellent model of multifactorial susceptibility to cancer. The study of PMZN allows to deepen scientific understanding of the mechanisms of carcinogenesis, to develop approaches to improve the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of malignant tumors. The study of the gene profile of various tumors creates the prerequisites for the development of not only general principles of targeted therapy for a specific type of neoplasm, but also their therapeutic individualization.